

Using a SNR Digital Twin for Failure Management

Luis Velasco*, Sima Barzegar, and Marc Ruiz

Optical Communications Group (GCO), Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), Barcelona, Spain

*e-mail: luis.velasco@upc.edu

ABSTRACT

The development of Digital Twins to represent the optical transport network might enable multiple applications for network operation, including automation and fault management. In this work, we use GNP_y as a Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) digital twin of the optical network for failure management applications. The methodology proposed for failure management consists in comparing the QoT measured in the transponders with the one estimated using the digital twin and try to explain detected deviations as changes in the value of input parameters of the Quality of Transmission (QoT) model representing the optical devices, like noise figure (NF) in optical amplifiers (OA) and reduced Optical SNR in the Wavelength Selective Switches (WSS). By applying reverse engineering, the value of those modeling parameters can be estimated as a function of the observed QoT of the lightpaths. Experiments reveal high accuracy estimation of modeling parameters, and results obtained by simulation show large anticipation of soft-failure detection and localization, as well as accurate identification of degradations before they have a major impact on the network.

Keywords: Digital Twins, Failure Management, Network Automation.

1 INTRODUCTION

With the introduction of 5G and beyond services, more autonomous, efficient and reliable optical networks are required in all network segments, from core to metro and access [1]. In that regard, Machine Learning (ML) has received special attention and several works have demonstrated its benefit to improve optical communications and for network automation (see e.g., [2], [3]). The low computational requirements of ML models for inference, once trained, make them very attractive to solve hard computational problems. For example, the authors in [4] proposed ML-based models for QoT estimation in single domain network scenarios, while the authors in [5] extended it to multidomain scenarios. In contrast, the well-known analytical model Split-Step Fourier Method (SSFM) [6] solves the nonlinear Schrödinger equation numerically with high accuracy but has high computational requirements, which limits its utilization for real-time operations and in dynamic optical network scenarios. ML, SSFM, and other methods can help in the control and management of optical networks, and are suitable tools to solve dedicated, isolated network problems. However, they fail to provide a holistic representation of the network with high accuracy and, simultaneously, low computational complexity. In this context, the use of a digital twin has been proposed to improve lightpath provisioning, QoT estimation, fault management, etc. [7]. Other initiative is the open-source project GNP_y [8], which implements the Gaussian Noise (GN) model [9] to estimate the signal's Linear Interference (LI) noise and NLI noise powers. GNP_y provides independent models for fiber propagation, optical amplifiers, and ROADMs, which can be concatenated to estimate the QoT of an optical connection. The use of GNP_y as a SNR digital twin of the optical network was suggested by the authors in [10], where the output of the models was analyzed. This paper summarizes the MESARTHIM methodology proposed in [10] for soft-failure detection, identification, localization, and severity estimation and provides an update of the architecture.

2 THE MESARTHIM METHODOLOGY

The performance of optical devices can degrade and such degradation might start with a low impact on the Quality of Transmission (QoT) of the supported lightpaths (soft-failure). However, it can degenerate into a hard-failure if the device itself is not repaired or replaced, or if an external cause responsible for the degradation is not properly addressed.

Our proposed architecture for soft-failure analysis is illustrated in Fig. 1. The optical layer consists of a disaggregated set of ROADMs and TRXs, and a set of optical links with a number of In-Line OAs interconnecting ROADMs. The control plane includes: *i*) a Network Controller to program the network devices; *ii*) an MDA system [12] that includes the telemetry system in charge of collating measurements from the data plane, analyses the data and issues recommendations to the network controller, as well as notifications regarding failures; and *iii*) a QoT digital twin based on GNP_y that estimates the SNR of the lightpaths and it is used for connection provisioning and for failure analytics. The MDA system stores a replica of the operational databases (DB) that are synchronized from the network controller. In addition, it collects measurements from the optical devices with a given periodicity and stores them in a *Measurements DB*; in this work, we assume that the MDA collects SNR samples from the TRXs every 15 minutes. These measurements are used by MESARTHIM to: *i*) estimate those modeling parameters related to optical devices (resources); *ii*) analyze the evolution of the measured SNR and that of the modeling parameters to detect any degradation as soon as it appears; and *iii*) determine the severity of the degradation based on the foreseen impact on the performance of the lightpaths.

Fig. 1. Overview of the proposed failure analytics architecture and the MESARTHIM methodology

Fig. 1 also sketches the MESARTHIM methodology implemented in the MDA system. Specifically, the following building blocks can be identified: (1) the *Surveillance* block that analyzes the SNR measurements and the value of modeling parameters to detect any meaningful degradation (e.g., by threshold crossing); (2) the *Localization* block that localizes the soft-failure; (3) the *Find Modeling Configuration* block that finds the most likely value of the modeling parameters of a given resource, so it results into SNR values of the lightpaths being supported by such resources similar to those that have been actually measured; (4) the *soft-failure Identification* block that, assuming a resource has been localized as the source of the soft-failure, finds what is the modeling parameter responsible for such failure; and (5) the *Severity Estimation* block that estimates whether and when the soft-failure will degenerate into a hard-failure. In addition, two internal repositories are used: *i*) the *Device Modeling Config DB* with the evolution of the value of modeling parameters along time for every resource; and *ii*) the *Network Diagnosis DB* that stores historical data for analysis purposes. The MESARTHIM manager coordinates those blocks to achieve intelligent QoT analysis, as well as manages the interface with the QoT digital twin.

3 FIND MODELING CONFIGURATION

The *FindModeling Configuration* block, estimates the most likely modeling configuration of a given resource r . Given the ranges of feasible configuration values \mathbb{V} of r , the configuration estimation problem consists in finding the most likely values v , by minimizing the error (computed as mean squared error $-MSE$) between the measured (S) and the estimated (\hat{S}) SNR for the set of lightpaths being supported by r , $P(r)$, i.e.:

$$\min_{v \in \mathbb{V}} MSE(S(P(r)), \hat{S}(P(r)|v)) \quad (1)$$

The SNR estimation $\hat{S}(\cdot)$ is obtained by calling the QoT digital twin and thus, the optimization problem in Eq. (1) cannot be solved by traditional methods like *Steepest Descent*, which are based on computing the gradient of the function to be minimized. In view of that, the *findLikelyModelingConfig()* procedure uses the *modelingConfigSearch()* one (Algorithm I) to solve the optimization problem in Eq. (1). The algorithm interrogates the QoT digital twin with different values of the parameters and the configuration entailing the lowest error with respect to the SNR values measured is returned. The procedure assumes that: *i*) the function is convex in \mathbb{V} , i.e., there is just one minimum that is the global minimum (tests supporting this assumption will be carried out); and *ii*) there is just one of the modeling parameters of r with a value different than the initially found. The procedure fixes the value(s) of the parameter(s) and requests the QoT digital twin to compute, with such configuration, the SNR values of the lightpaths being supported by r . By computing the *mse()* function, the procedure determines if such configuration is likely enough or if more queries to the QoT tool are needed.

As calls to the QoT tool are time consuming, *modelingConfigSearch()* targets at minimizing them; instead of using the brute force and request the estimation of the SNR for the whole range of possible values, the procedure uses the projection of two points to determine the next value of the parameters to be used for the estimation. As

Algorithm I. Modeling Config Search	
INPUT: P, r, v_{min}, v_{max}	OUTPUT: $\langle v, m \rangle$
1:	$\langle v, m \rangle \leftarrow configDB.getMin(); numIters \leftarrow 0$
2:	while $m > epsilon$ AND $numIters++ < MaxIters$ do
3:	$\langle v_l, m_l \rangle, \langle v_r, m_r \rangle \leftarrow configDB.getNeighbours(v)$
4:	$v_a \leftarrow intersect(v, m, v_l, m_l, v_{min}, v_{max})$
5:	$v_b \leftarrow intersect(v, m, v_r, m_r, v_{min}, v_{max})$
6:	if $v_a = v_l$ then $v_a \leftarrow (v + v_l) / 2$
7:	if $v_b = v_r$ then $v_b \leftarrow (v + v_r) / 2$
8:	$m_a \leftarrow configDB.getConfig(v_a)$
9:	if $m_a = None$ then
10:	$m_a \leftarrow MSE(P.SNR, QTool(P, r, v_a))$
11:	$configDB.addConfig(\langle v_a, m_a \rangle)$
12:	$m_b \leftarrow configDB.getConfig(v_b)$
13:	if $m_b = None$ then
14:	$m_b \leftarrow MSE(P.SNR, QTool(P, r, v_b))$
15:	$configDB.addConfig(\langle v_b, m_b \rangle)$
16:	$\langle v, m \rangle \leftarrow configDB.getMin()$
17:	return $\langle v, m \rangle$

parameters typically evolve smoothly in time when devices are affected by a soft-failure, it also stores the last configuration(s) in the *Device Modeling Config DB*; every time it is called, it uses such configurations as starting points for the search aiming at finding the optimal solution fast.

4 SURVEILLANCE AND LOCALIZATION

We assume that surveillance is carried out periodically, e.g., after at least one new SNR measurement has been collected for every lightpath in the network. The *surveillance* block analyzes the evolution of the value of modeling parameters and returns the resources with the found likely modeling configuration with a subset of lightpaths indicating that some soft-failure has been detected. The SNR measurements of *all* the lightpaths in the network supported by a resource are used to estimate the most likely modeling configuration of such resource using the *Find Modeling Config* block. The found modeling configuration is stored and its evolution is analyzed to detect any meaningful degradation, e.g., a significant trend and/or variation.

Algorithm II details the pseudocode of the *Surveillance* algorithm; it first initializes the *SR* data structure (line 1 in Algorithm II) and creates the set of resources with the lightpaths that each one supports (line 2). Next, for every single resource, the algorithm uses the last SNR measurements to find the current value of the parameters modeling the resource, which are stored in the *Device Modeling Config DB* by the *Find Modeling Configuration* block (lines 3-6). The behavior of the modeling parameters evolution is and, if a non-stationary pattern is found, the resource is added to the *SR* set (lines 7-9). It is worth noting that this analysis could detect soft-failures that have not yet had a relevant impact on the lightpaths (i.e., the SNR degradation threshold has not been exceeded yet), as parameters and SNR are not linearly related.

Algorithm II. Surveillance Algorithm		Algorithm III. Soft-Failure Localization Algorithm	
INPUT: $G, P, T, current_t$	OUTPUT: SR	INPUT: SR	OUTPUT: iSF, mSF
1: $SR \leftarrow \emptyset$		1: for each r in SR do	
2: $R = \{ \langle resource, P \rangle \} \leftarrow$ GroupPathsByResources(G, P)		2: $Rr \leftarrow \emptyset$	
3: for each r in R do		3: for each r' in $SR \mid r \neq r'$ do	
4: for each p in $r.P$ do		4: if $r.P = r'.P$ then $Rr \leftarrow Rr \cup \{r, r'\}$	
5: $p.snr \leftarrow$ getMonitoringData($p, current_t$)		5: $SR \leftarrow SR - Rr$	
6: findLikelyModelingConfig($r, current_t$)		6: $iSF \leftarrow \emptyset$	
7: $r.evol \leftarrow$ configDB.SELECT(r, T)		7: for each r in SR do	
8: hasBehavior \leftarrow findBehavior(r)		8: if $r.P \cap r'.P = \emptyset \forall r' \in SR \mid r \neq r'$ then	
9: if hasBehavior then $SR \leftarrow SR \cup \{r\}$		9: $iSF \leftarrow iSF \cup \{r\}$;	
10: return SR		10: $SR \leftarrow SR - \{r\}$	
		11: return iSF, SR	

In case that the surveillance phase has identified a set of suspicious resources, Algorithm III localizes the soft-failures. The algorithm first removes the suspicious resources that explain the very same set of lightpaths (lines 1-6 in Algorithm III), as localization is not yet possible in those cases. Next, the resources that explain the SNR of complete subsets of lightpaths are localized and classified as *independent* soft-failures, iSF (lines 6-10). The rest of the suspicious resources are related to soft-failures that affect common subsets of lightpaths, so a given lightpath can be affected by more than one soft-failure.

5 SOFT-FAILURE IDENTIFICATION AND SEVERITY ESTIMATION

Let us now focus on the *Soft-Failure Identification* and the *Severity Estimation* blocks, which are assumed to be executed as soon as degradation is detected and localized, via device configuration analysis. These blocks make MESARTIM able to generate notifications to the network controller containing not only the list of degraded lightpaths, but also the estimated time for the soft-failure to degrade into a hard-failure.

Let us imagine that the surveillance and localization analysis detected some degradation at time t and therefore, non-empty ISR and/or MSF sets were found. Let us define *state* as the combination of the estimated modeling configuration of the resources that are involved, and the SNR experienced by the supported lightpaths. With the aim of an accurate diagnosis, it is interesting not only to analyze the current state but also to predict its future evolution. It is for this very reason that historical data (within a pre-defined time window) are gathered from telemetry and device config DBs and stored in the *Network Diagnosis DB*. The evolution of each parameter (lightpaths' SNR and device modeling config parameters) is analyzed individually using time series forecasting techniques. By using different techniques with different parametrization, several expected evolutions can be obtained as a practical way to generate different likely projections for parameter degradation.

For illustrative purposes, let us analyze an example of the evolution of three parameters selected from a hypothetical state: the SNR of a given lightpath affected by an SNR degradation, as well as the NF and P-max parameters modeling an OA traversed by that lightpath. Fig. 2 presents three time-evolutions of the OA modeling parameters and SNR, and their analysis at current time t . At this time, the failure has been correctly localized in the selected OA; however, the cause of the degradation (either NF or P-max) is still unclear. This is the reason behind performing the estimation and evolution analysis for all modeling parameters; such analysis is carried out following forecasting techniques. Three curves representing the *upper* (f_u), *centered* (f_c), and *lower* (f_l)

projected possible evolutions are depicted for each parameter. Based on such projections, monitored data are evaluated and an *indicator* (ϕ) is computed and used to discard modeling parameters while identifying the one that is the most likely to be the real cause of the observed performance degradation. Hence, the indicator provides large values when the modeling parameter is far from the expected behavior of an affected parameter. The obtained indicator is accumulated with the values computed previously, and identification is positive when the parameter with the lowest accumulated indicator is far from all the rest of the parameters with a significantly higher accumulated one. This evidence can be easily observed by setting up a threshold allowing the discrimination of low and high accumulated indicator modeling parameters.

Once the *Soft-Failure Identification* block has found enough evidence of the modeling parameter explaining the soft-failure, the *Severity Estimation* block uses the centered projection of the evolution of such modeling parameter to estimate the likely evolution of the SNR for the affected lightpaths (i.e., those being supported by the localized resource). Analyzing such evolution, it is easy to check whether any lightpath would exceed a given threshold. For instance, the minimum SNR defined by its modulation format and bit rate.

6 CONCLUSION

QoT estimation is typically carried out during the provisioning phase and in-operation planning to ensure that computed lightpaths will provide zero post-FEC errors, assuming some values for the QoT model input parameters related to the optical devices in the network. In this paper, QoT estimation was used for the reverse process, i.e., given the real measured QoT of a set of lightpaths, we were interested in estimating the value of the modeling parameters of the optical devices.

Because of the non-linear relation between lightpaths' QoT and the value of the modeling parameters, the ability to estimate the value of such parameters opens the opportunity to analyze its evolution, which can be as a result of, e.g., aging, temperature variations, etc. The proposed MESARTHIM methodology combines analysis of the evolution of the monitoring QoT and their transformation into the estimated modeling parameters space, not only for the degradation detection, but also for its localization, identification, and severity estimation.

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Fig. 2. Example of identification and severity estimation at time t .